

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

The Effect of Work Facilities on Employee Performance in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the use of work facilities on the performance of employees at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency. The data collection techniques used were questionnaires and documentation with a population of 36 people. While the data analysis technique used is a descriptive statistical analysis using percentages and for inferential statistical analysis techniques using data normality test, product-moment correlation analysis, and simple linear regression analysis. The results showed that the working facilities at the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Office of Gowa Regency were in a very good category. The performance of employees at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency is in the very good category which is seen from 1) quantity (90%) 2) quality (88%) 3) timeliness (89%) 4) attendance (89%) , and 5) ability to work together (82%). Based on the product-moment correlation test analysis, it is stated that there is a positive and significant effect of the use of work facilities on the performance of employees at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency by 52%, stated that it is accepted with a strong level of influence. From the results of simple linear regression analysis, it shows that there is an influence of the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency.

Keywords: *Work facilities, performance, employees.*

INTRODUCTION

Every organization in carrying out activities to achieve its goals has several factors that are interconnected and influential (Amirullah & Saleh, 2015; Jamaluddin, Salam, Yunus, & Akib, 2017; Lie, 2016). One of these factors is very important to be used to

drive the other factor, namely human resources (Blaga & Boer, 2012; Boer & Blaga, 2012; Suhariadi, 2013). Therefore, organizations are required to manage and optimize human resources. The human resources to be employed must be professional (Lendzion, 2015; Raudeliūnienė & Meidutė-Kavaliauskienė, 2014; Saitua-Iribar, Andicoechea-Arondo, & Albizu-Gallastegi, 2014; Suhariadi, 2013; Enor, & Chime 2015).

Achieving company goals requires employees who are following the requirements in the company, and must also be able to carry out the tasks that have been determined by the company (Sari, Jamaluddin, Saleh, & Arhas, 2020; Sutrisno & Sunarsi, 2019). Every company will always try to improve the performance of its employees, with the hope of achieving company goals (Hewagama, Boxall, Cheung, & Hutchison, 2019; Peng, Lee, & Lu, 2020; Pitafi, Kanwal, Ali, Khan, & Waqas Ameen, 2018). To achieve the goals set by an office, it must be supported by adequate work facilities so that the work process can take place efficiently and effectively. (Kiyak, Namazi, & Kahana, 1997; Pitafi et al., 2018).

Performance is the implementation of a plan that has been prepared, the implementation of performance is carried out by human resources who have the ability, competence, motivation, and interests (Escribá-Carda, Balbastre-Benavent, & Teresa Canet-Giner, 2017; Kelidbari, Fadaei, & Ebrahimi, 2016; Van Thielen, Bauwens, Audenaert, Van Waeyenberg, & Decramer, 2018; Ishak, Niswaty & Guntur 2020). How the organization values and treats human resources which will influence their attitudes and behavior in carrying out their performance. Conceptually, performance can be seen from two aspects, namely individual employee performance and organizational performance. Employee performance is the result of individual work within the organization. While organizational performance is the totality of work achieved by an organization. Employee performance and organizational performance are closely related. The achievement of organizational goals cannot be separated from the resources owned by the organization that is used or run by employees who play an active role as actors in achieving the goals of the organization (Björkman & Lu, 1999; Gümüş, Apak, Gümüş, & Kurban, 2013; O'Sullivan, 2010).

There are several opinions about the definition of performance put forward by experts and experts with different definition formulations. (Rue & Byar, 1981) said that performance is the level of achievement of results. The performance plan relates to the operations, program activities, and mission of the organization. Murphy and Cleveland say that performance is the quality of behavior that is task-oriented and work-oriented (Irek 2016: Irek & Charles 2012; Ismail Nawawi Uha, 2013).

James B. Whittaker argues "that performance measurement is a management tool used to improve the quality of decision making and accountability. Performance measurement is also used to assess the achievement of goals and objectives (goals and objectives).

Through performance measurement, it is expected that government agencies can find out the performance in a certain period. With the existence of performance measurement, the activities and programs of government agencies can be measured and evaluated. Furthermore, from performance measurement, each agency can be compared with similar agencies, so that rewards and disciplinary action can be carried out more objectively.

Work facilities are a means of supporting physical office activities and are used in

normal office activities, have a relatively permanent period of use, and provide benefits for the future. Work facilities are very important for the office because they can support employee performance, such as in completing work. Work facilities are a means of supporting physical office activities and are used in normal office activities, have a relatively permanent period of use, and provide benefits for the future. Work facilities are very important for the office because they can support employee performance, such as in completing work.

In an office, to achieve a goal, supporting tools are needed that are used in processes or activities in the office. The facilities used by each office vary in shape, type, and benefit. The greater the activity of an office, the more complete facilities and means of support in the process of activities to achieve these goals. Seeing the current reality in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency, it appears that there is a possibility that there is a lack of facilities such as inadequate office machines, inadequate office equipment, transportation equipment, and other office stationery that can support employee work processes so that they affect on the performance of employees in completing their work.

METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach, where the type of research used is descriptive research. Descriptive research is a study conducted with the main objective of providing an objective description or description of a situation. There are 2 variables in this study, the independent variable is work facilities, while The dependent variable is employee performance. To measure this variable using a questionnaire instrument (questionnaire) using a Likert scale which is arranged based on variable indicators. (Sugiyono, 2017) argues that, the population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher for the study, and then the conclusion is drawn, the total population in this study is 36 respondents. The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2018). The determination of sampling according to Arikunto, namely if the subject is less than 100 then it is better to take all of them so that the research is a population study. The data collection techniques used in this study were observation, questionnaires, and documentation.

An activity that is quite important in the entire research process is data processing. With data processing, it can be seen about the meaning of the data that has been collected so that the results of the research will be immediately known. The data analysis technique in this study used descriptive statistical analysis design and inferential statistical analysis, for that data analysis technique used was percentage analysis by presenting each question. to determine the effect of work facilities on employee performance in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency. For inferential statistical analysis, using the data normality test to determine the normality of a data, simple linear regression analysis is used to measure the strength of the variables, and product-moment correlation analysis is used to test whether there is a significant influence between work facility

variables and employee performance at the Office of Investment. and One Stop Services in Gowa Regency.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data presented in this study are data obtained from the percentage of questionnaires that have been given to 36 employees who are the research samples which are intended to determine the effect of work facilities on employee performance in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services, Gowa Regency:

Work Facilities

The data presented in this study are data obtained from a questionnaire score that has been given to 36 employees who are the study population which is intended to determine the effect of work facilities on employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency.

In the work facility variable there are 2 indicators, namely: 1) Work Equipment Facilities, 2) Work Equipment Facilities, the following scores are obtained.

Table. 1.

Results of Data Analysis Per Work Facility Variable Indicator (X)

No.	Indicator	N	N	%	Category
1	Work Tool Facilities	990	1080	92.00	Very good
2	Work Equipment Facilities	2196	2520	87.00	Very good
Total		3186	3600	89.00	Very good

Source: 2020 Questionnaire Results

$$\% = \frac{\text{Value obtained}}{\text{number of items} \times \text{ideal score} \times \text{number of respondents}} \times 100\%$$

$$\% \times \frac{3186}{20 \times 5 \times 36} \times 100 = \frac{3186}{3600} \times 100\% = 88,5\%$$

The results of data analysis in the table above, it can be seen that the work tool facility indicator is in the highest percentage of 92% and is in the very good category because the conditions of the work tools in the form of computers and laminating machines are well maintained and fit for use. Work equipment facilities are in the very good category with a percentage of 87%.

Employee Performance

To know the description of employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency. The data presented in this study are data obtained from the scores from the questionnaires that have been filled in by the respondents. In the employee performance variable, there are 5 (five) indicators, namely: 1) quantity,

2) quality, 3) timeliness, 4) attendance, and 5) ability to work together, the following scores are obtained:

Table 2.

Results of Data Analysis Per Employee Performance Variable Indicator (Y)

No.	Indicator	n	N	%	Category
1	Quantity	484	540	90	Very good
2	Quality	793	900	88	Very good
3	Punctuality	797	900	89	Very good
4	Presence	480	540	89	Very good
5	Cooperative Ability	591	720	82	Very good
Total		3145	3600	87.00	Very good

Source: 2020 Questionnaire Results

$$\% = \frac{\text{value obtained}}{\text{number of items} \times \text{ideal score} \times \text{number of respondents}} \times 100\%$$

$$\% = \frac{3145}{20 \times 5 \times 36} \times 100 = \frac{3145}{3600} \times 100\% = 87,36\%$$

From the results of data analysis in the table and diagram above, the employee performance variable shows that the quantity indicator gets the highest percentage of 90.00% with a very good category level because employees have the quantity, ability and complete their work well, the quality gets a percentage of 88.00% with a very good category level, timeliness got a percentage of 89.00% with a very good category level, attendance got a percentage of 89.00% with a very good category, and the last indicator with the ability to work together got a percentage of 82.00% with a very good category level.

Effect of Work Facilities on Employee Performance

Table 3.

Summary of Data Normality Test Results with Sig. 5%.

Variable	X ² _{hitung}	X ² _{tabel}	Df	Information
Work Facilities	15.333	18.307	10	Normal
Employee Performance	20.000	31.410	20	Normal

Source: Results of statistical analysis through the SPSS Program 22

Based on table 3, it can be seen that the results of the data normality test work, that the work facility variable (X) is stated to be normally distributed because it has met the requirements of X²count (15.333) is smaller (≤) than X² table with DF 10 of 18,307. Likewise with employee performance variables (Y) is declared normally distributed

because it also meets the requirements X^2 count (20,000) is smaller (\leq) than X^2 table with DF 20 of 31,410.

Table 4.
Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variable	β	F_{hitung}	Sig.	Sig.
Constanta	39.539			0.000
		37.391	0.000	
Work Facilities	0.560			0.000

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis through the SPSS Program. 22

Based on the table above, it is known that the calculation of the simple linear regression equation obtained the values of $\alpha = 39,539$ and $\beta = 0.560$ so that the regression equation is $\hat{Y} = 39,539 + 0.560 (X)$.

From the results of the F-test calculation, it is obtained that F_{count} is 37,391 and F_{table} (0.05: 1: 33) is 4.14, which means that F_{count} is greater than F_{table} . Because $F_{count} > F_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

Table 5.
Rangkuman Hasil Pengujian Korelasi Product Moment dengan signifikan 5%
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.724 ^a	.524	.510	3.38291

Based on the results of the calculation of the product-moment correlation, the r count is 0.724, by looking at the guidelines in table 2 it is written in the correlation coefficient of 0.724 in the interval 0.60 - 0.799 with a strong relationship level.

To test for a significant relationship, whether any relationship was found that applies to the entire population. Whether there is a significant correlation between these results or not, then compared to r_{count} with r_{table} with a significant level of 5% and respondent (N) = 36, then the r_{table} is 0.329.

From the results of the product-moment correlation test, it can be stated that there is a significant relationship between work facilities and employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency because r_{count} (0.724) is greater than r_{table} (0.329) then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. The coefficient of determination obtained $r^2 = 0.524$ or 52.00%. This means that employee performance is determined by the work facility of 52.00% while the rest is determined by other factors not examined in this study at 48.00%.

DISCUSSION

Work Tool Facilities

An employee or worker cannot perform the work assigned to him without working tools. Even these work tools are divided into two types: management work tools and operational work tools. Management work tools in the form of rules that define authority and power in carrying out their obligations. Operational work tools are all objects or goods that function as tools that are directly used in production. This definition includes all work equipment in the office such as computer machines and laminating machines. In this indicator aspect, it shows that work facilities in the form of computer machines and laminating machines are in the very good category (Table 1). Where computer machines and laminating machines can support the achievement of work goals with conditions that are suitable for use, are used for work activities, are easy to use, and accelerate in the work process, and their placement is properly arranged.

Work tool facilities at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service, Gowa Regency as a form of service to employees that can support performance in meeting employee needs to increase employee productivity. Thus the working equipment facilities provided by the office, such as 13 computers, 10 printers, and 2 laminating machines are very supportive of employees in their work because of these facilities.

Work Equipment Facilities

Work equipment is all objects or items used in work but not directly for production, but functions as a smoother and refresher in work. This aspect shows that work equipment facilities are in the very good category (Table 1). Included in this work equipment are office cabinets, work desks, and chairs, office telephones, office household appliances, waiting rooms for visitors, fans and TVs, office stationery, and parking lots. All of these are used for work equipment to function very well. both in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services, Gowa Regency.

The use of work facilities at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services of Gowa Regency can be carried out well, this is inseparable from the way the leadership makes use of the use of available work facilities or by presenting work facilities that are not yet available. This is also inseparable from the existence of leaders in improving employee performance with the leadership's efforts in improving employee performance through supervision, guidance, and training.

With work equipment facilities that have been prepared such as 47 office desks and chairs, 8 office cabinets, and other work equipment so that employees will feel safe working and can generate morale for the expected results.

The use of work facilities has a very important role, the more or more varied work facilities are used, the employees will be motivated to work. The more quality work facilities used, the better employee performance will be.

Employee Performance

Employee performance is seen from the work results of employees in the use of certain time and speed in completing office tasks and responsibilities. Based on the results of research data on this indicator, the quantity is in the very good category. Because employees can master the assigned tasks and can complete their work as quickly and as possible. It can also be seen in the previous discussion that the mission of DPM-PTSP is to improve human resources and office administration governance to achieve work efficiency, effectiveness, and comfort. What is provided by employees in the office are employees who complete their work appropriately and are accountable to the community for what they do? Work quality can be measured from employees' perceptions of the quality of work produced and perfection related to employee skills and abilities. Based on research data on this indicator, quality is in the very good category (Table 2). Due to employees who can master the given field, have experience with many things, can solve problems by themselves, prioritize office interests, have good quality skills. It can also be seen from the mission of DPM - PTSP which can realize licensing and non-licensing services in a professional and accountable manner.

Measured from employees' perceptions of activity from the beginning of time to output. Can complete work at a predetermined time and maximize the time available for other activities. Based on the results of research data on this indicator, timeliness is in the very good category (Table 2). Where employees can complete work carefully and on time, can maximize time for other activities, and be disciplined in carrying out tasks and jobs. It can be seen from the mission DPM-PTSP, namely employees of accuracy in completing work by not wasting time and using the best possible time.

The level of experience of employees is very important, especially when employees come and go from work according to official regulations. The attendance level can determine employee performance. Based on the results of research data on this indicator, it is in the very good category (Table 2). Where employees come and come home from work on time according to official regulations. It can be seen in the attachment of employee absences for a month that the attendance of employees from fingerprint absences in the office is following the results of the questionnaire obtained.

The measure of an employee's ability to in the work of things have a very positive effect on work in the office because it can produce maximum work. Based on the results of research data on this indicator, the ability to work together is in the very good category. Where employees do the job as well as possible and on time to complete the work.

The Influence of Work Facilities on Employee Performance in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency

Based on the results of hypothesis testing between work facility variables on employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency, where the two variables have a significant relationship. This means that the

hypothesis in this study "it is suspected that there is an effect of work facilities on employee performance in the office. The Department of Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services, Gowa Regency, was declared to be accepted with a strong degree of influence.

Work facilities are also a support for improving employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency. This cannot be separated from the importance of using work facilities as a means of facilitating employee processes. Thus, the work facilities provided by the office such as office work equipment such as computers and laminating machines and included in this work equipment are office cabinets, work desks, and chairs, office telephones, office household appliances, waiting rooms for visitors, fans, and TV, office stationery, and parking lots that support employees in working because these facilities can help employees to make it easier to complete their work optimally.

In the research conducted by Ambarwati and Suryani, it was found that work facilities had a significant effect on the performance of village officials in Wonoboyo District, Tumanggung Regency. The provision of complete facilities is also one of the driving forces for work. An office must have various kinds of work facilities such as office buildings, computers, desks, cupboards, and other supporting facilities such as official vehicles.

The use of work facilities will have a good influence on employee performance, with optimal use of work facilities will further stimulate employee performance at work which in turn will improve employee performance indirectly.

With work facilities that have been prepared, employees feel comfortable at work and can generate morale to get good results and are expected to be following the wishes of the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency.

Good work facilities are an important factor in improving employee performance. From the results of research that has been carried out at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency, it can be concluded that the work facilities are very good, where the work of employees is greatly helped by the existence of appropriate and adequate work facilities for employees. The Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency has made efforts to further improve work facilities so that employee performance is better.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion of the results of this study, regarding the effect of work facilities on employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency, the results of this study can be concluded as follows:

1. Work facilities (X) at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency are in the very good category, in terms of indicators of work equipment facilities and work equipment facilities.

2. Employee performance (Y) at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services of Gowa Regency is in the very good category, this is in terms of indicators of quantity, quality, timeliness, attendance, and the ability to work together.
3. There is a significant influence between work facilities on employee performance at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency. It means that the hypothesis that is proposed is "it is suspected that there is an influence of work facilities on the performance of employees in the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency", it is stated that it is accepted with a strong level of influence.

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